

SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS FOR HARVESTING ROOTS

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Agricultural products, including root fruits, make up a large part of a person's vital needs. Therefore, cultivating root fruits and harvesting crops without harm is one of the main tasks of agricultural events. Considering the above, it is of great importance to have information about the scientific research and scientific results achieved by our scientists in this field. If the root crop seeds sown in the spring are harvested in the middle of summer, the one in summer is harvested in late October and early November. These two collection seasons will vary from one another according to the soil-climatic conditions. This in turn complicates the harvesting of root crops. An improved carrot digging is designed to harvest the autumn harvest, and applying it for the summer harvest is not recommended. Because of the fact that during the summer season, we are more likely to damage the crop because the soil conditions are hot and dry. Improved carrot digging reduces manual labor and improves work productivity. It is recommended to use a universal root crop harvester to harvest the crop in the summer season since the heat and dry conditions of the soil during the summer season can cause an increase in the level of root crop damage in driving the crop to the surface of the earth. Another reason for the increase in damage is that solid soil cuts should not be crushed because this humidity is low.

Keywords: digging, root crop harvester, tuber, ploughshare, root digger, gearbox, potato digger, energy indicator, carrot digger; root harvester; authors, citations, Scopus database.

1. Introduction

Agriculture is one of the most important parts of any country [1]. It is for this reason that the importance of improving the efficiency of harvesting, including reducing energy consumption and increasing the speed of the harvester, is increasing day by day [2]. To increase the productivity and sustainability of agriculture, technologies and technical means of tillage, sowing and harvesting of agricultural crops and their primary processing have been developed and improved [3], [4]. An important reserve for increasing crop yields is creating optimal soil conditions for the development of the root system of plants [5]. With the development of science and technology, scientists have developed many technological methods of cultivating agricultural crops (Udompant et al., 2021). In many countries of the world, research work is underway aimed at developing new scientific and technical foundations for resource-saving technologies that ensure the movement and separation of a layer with dug roots at lower energy costs, as well as separation from the soil and laying them in a swath without damage [8], [9]. In this regard, an important task is considered to be the implementation of scientific research in such areas as the provision of energy-saving methods with the development of sectional undercut plowshares and the use of side discs, the development of paddle beaters to intensify the soil separation process [2], [10].

Currently, root crops are planted and cultivated on 30-35 million hectares of land all over the world [11].

The cultivation and harvesting of root crops is an important component of agricultural production in almost all countries. At the same time, much attention is paid to the development of highly efficient and resource-saving technical means that ensure the digging of root crops with minimal energy consumption [12], [13]. The variety of climates, soil conditions and water supply of each region around the world, causes a variety of difficulties in the harvesting of root crops. For example, in the soil and climatic conditions of Uzbekistan (high summer temperatures, low relative humidity, soil compaction after irrigation), in the process of harvesting root crops, the soil of the tuberous layer disintegrates into large soil lumps that are harder than root crops, thereby making it difficult to separate it from root crops at the elevator. This circumstance is the main reason that prevents the introduction of root and tuber harvesters [14]. When harvesting the root fruit crop, it is desirable to use the necessary techniques, depending on the season [15].

In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the introduction of science, technology and best agriculture practices. To increase the productivity and sustainability of agriculture, technologies and technical means of tillage, sowing and harvesting of agricultural crops and their primary processing have been developed and improved. An important reserve for increasing crop yields is creating optimal soil conditions for the development of the root system of plants. With the development of science and technology, scientists have developed

many technological methods of cultivating agricultural crops.

In many countries of the world, research work is underway aimed at developing new scientific and technical foundations for resource-saving technologies that ensure the movement and separation of a layer with dug roots at lower energy costs, as well as separation from the soil and laying them in a swath without damage. In this regard, an important task is considered to be the implementation of scientific research in such areas as the provision of energy saving methods with the development of sectional undercut plowshares and the use of side discs, the development of paddle beaters to intensify the soil separation process.

Growing and harvesting root crops is an important component of the republic's agricultural production. At the same time, much attention is paid to the development of highly efficient and resource-saving technical means that ensure the digging of root crops with minimal energy consumption. In the soil and climatic conditions of our Republic (high summer temperatures, low relative humidity, soil compaction after irrigation), in the process of harvesting root crops, the soil of the tuberous layer disintegrates into large soil lumps that are more hard than root crops, thereby making it difficult to separate it from root crops at the elevator. This circumstance is the main reason that prevents the introduction of root and tuber harvesters.

Currently, vegetable growing needs the introduction of advanced technologies, equipped with highly efficient technical means adapted to the economic and soil-climatic conditions of the republic. The analysis of the current state of cultivation and harvesting of root crops in the republic showed that in vegetable growing, harvesting of carrot tubers is one of the most labor-intensive operations with a low level of mechanization [1, 2, 3, 4]. When using carrot diggers, the process of selecting tubers after digging them out is performed manually. This circumstance, in turn, leads to an increase in labor costs for the production of products. Numerous studies presented that in the technological process of root crop harvesters, the main thing was to separate the tubers from the clumps of soil without damage under any operating conditions.

The results of the analysis of the quality indicators of the existing root crop harvester showed that the agrotechnical requirements for digging root tubers were most fully met, mainly when working on light soils with optimal humidity and not containing strong soil lumps [5]. In difficult soil and climatic conditions, the machines do not fully meet the agrotechnical requirements for the process of digging tubers. As a result, losses and damage to tubers are quite large, which worsens the marketability of products and, as a result, reduces the cost of its implementation. Therefore, the reduction of losses and the degree of damage to tubers during the development of the root-tuberizer through the use of new technical solutions that meet agrotechnical requirements, with minimal energy costs, is an ur-

gent task. Serial digging working bodies dig out the excess volume of the soil layer (row spacing zone) and as a result, the soil is unloaded in this zone, especially at high speeds of the unit, energy consumption increases, and there is a large loss of tubers. The digger for digging root tubers should provide high-quality, in accordance with agrotechnical requirements, digging with minimal energy consumption, be less metal-intensive and labor-intensive in maintenance.

On the basis of foreign experience in the design of root diggers and taking into account the soil and climatic features and the variety of physical, mechanical and technological properties of the soil in different periods of harvesting root crops, as well as agrotechnical requirements, the following requirements for the digger were formulated: 1) the digging working bodies of the root crop harvester should dig out the part of the bed where the nests with root tubers are located, without unloading the soil, which will reduce their traction resistance; 2) to ensure the maximum release of soil and plant impurities of the root crop harvester by using an intensifier, which will significantly reduce the energy and metal consumption of the separation process; 3) lay the potato harvesters in the roll with minimal damage, for which to ensure the damping of shock effects by reducing the height of the fall in the process of dropping them on the surface of the field, which reduces the complexity of assembling the tubers. Therefore, this scientific research was aimed at developing a more efficient method of harvesting tubers that provides the required quality of work with less energy consumption and greater productivity.

2. Materials and methods

In this article, we went to the selected publications on worldly knowledge from the research done. The search collects the English-language academic literature retrieved from the Scopus database for the period 1982-2022. The analysis was carried out in September 2022. A total of 201 publications were downloaded with the keywords "root and harvester". In the next step, articles were categorized according to the year of publication. A database of all peer-reviewed papers was then created, including the year of publication, authors' names, countries, publication type, journal name, number of citations per paper, the number of citations per journal, the percentage of publications by the topic cluster name and subject area. The analysis was performed using a CSV file, Microsoft Excel 2021, RIS, VOS viewer and Map chart. Figure 1 shows the flow of the selected methodology for the research.

A total of 203 research papers related to root harvesters were obtained from the Scopus database from 1982 to 2022. The number of yearly published papers was divided into two time periods. In the first period between 1982 and 2004 the number of papers fluctuated from 1 to 4 papers (Fig.2). In the second period between 2005 and 2022, the number of papers started to increase from 2009. The largest number of published papers was in 2019 with 22 papers which was 22 times more than the number of papers published in 2002.

Figure 2. Number of papers on root harvester issues in the world (1982-2022)

The interest in root harvesters started to considerably rise in the second period and the number of published papers consist 86,6% of the total number. However, in the first period, it covers only 13,4%. This research shows the significant concern in the subject of root harvesters.

Further analysis showed that 140 (70%) out of 201 published documents were research articles, followed by 49 (24%) conference papers, 2 (1%) book chapters, 8 (4%) reviews and 2 (1%) conference reviews. This information suggests that researchers preferred to publish in journals rather than in conferences (Fig.3).

Figure 3. Publication type on root harvester issue in the world

A wide variety of journals in different parts of the world are used by scholars to publish their research. The communication patterns of the scholars indicate that the total output was distributed across 121 journals published in 58 countries. Of these 10 journals pub-

lished 39 (32%) papers and the remaining 68% of papers were published in other journals. Table 1 lists the names of the 31 journals which published a minimum of 2 and a higher number of papers during the above-mentioned period.

Table 1.

List of the journals on harvester machine issues in the world			
Scopus Source title	Number	Scopus Source title	Number
International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering	7	Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov Series II Forestry Wood Industry Agricultural Food Engineering	2
Proceedings of SPIE The International Society for Optical Engineering	5	Electronics Switzerland	2
Smart Materials And Structures	5	Frontiers In Plant Science	2
Soil And Tillage Research	4	IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement	2
Agronomy	3	IFAC Proceedings Volumes IFAC Paper-sonline	2
Agronomy Research	3	Inmateh Agricultural Engineering	2
Economic Botany	3	Iop Conference Series Materials Science and Engineering	2
International Agricultural Engineering Journal	3	Journal of Agricultural Engineering	2
Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures	3	Journal of Vibration and Acoustics Transactions of the ASME	2
Zuckerindustrie	3	Nano Energy	2
AMA Agricultural Mechanization in Asia Africa and Latin America	2	Nongye Gongcheng Xuebao Transactions of The Chinese Society of Agricultural Engineering	2
Acta Horticulturae	2	Proceedings of the ASME Design Engineering Technical Conference	2
Advanced Materials Research	2	Soil Use and Management	2
Agriculture Switzerland	2	South African Journal of Botany	2
Applied Sciences Switzerland	2	Transactions of The American Society of Agricultural Engineers	2
Biological Conservation	2		

The second analyzing criteria is the name of publishing country and impact factor of the top 15 journals (Table 2). Of these fifteen journals were published three from the US, two of them from China, Germany, Switzerland and the other six countries have one journal each from UK, Netherlands, Spanish, Estonian, Japan,

Belgium. The average impact factor of the journals with the highest number of articles was 2,24. Among the 15 journals the *Soil and Tillage Research* had the highest impact factor and the *International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering* had the highest number of publications in this field.

Table 2.

Distribution of research output in prolific journals			
Journal	TNP (%)	Publishing country	IF
International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering	3,4%	China	2,08
Proceedings of SPIE The International Society for Optical Engineering	2,5%	US	0,38
Smart Materials And Structures	2,5%	UK	4,1
Soil and Tillage Research	2,0%	Netherlands	7,3
Agronomy	1,5%	Spanish	3,9
Agronomy Research	1,5%	Estonian	0,36
Economic Botany	1,5%	US	2,35
International Agricultural Engineering Journal	1,5%	China	0,12
Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures	1,5%	US	2,74
Zuckerindustrie	1,5%	Germany	0,24
AMA Agricultural Mechanization in Asia Africa and Latin America	1,0%	Japan	0,14
Acta Horticulturae	1,0%	Belgium	0,28
Advanced Materials Research	1,0%	Germany	3,2
Agriculture Switzerland	1,0%	Switzerland	3,49
Applied Sciences Switzerland	1,0%	Switzerland	3,02
Total:	24,1%		2,24

* TNP – Total number of publications, * IF – Impact factor

The soil-climate conditions of the region are very important in the harvesting of agricultural crops. The harvest of all types of root crops is located under the soil, and the condition of the soil (moisture, hardness, density, etc.) and mechanical composition affect the quality of work of harvesters [6-9].

Soil moisture has a great impact on the quality of work and power consumption of the working unit. Loamy soils stick to the working bodies in wet conditions and soil compaction occurs. In the dry state, large lumps are formed. In both cases, the process of sieving during the collection of root crops is worsened. However, at a certain moisture level, the soil is easily and well compacted, and a minimum amount of energy is spent during its processing. This condition of the soil is called maturity. Depending on the mechanical composition of the soil, its maturity occurs when the absolute humidity is 15...18% percent. According to the results of the research, the maturity of the soil also affects the speed of the aggregates [10-12].

When the soil is ripe, it is advisable to organize the work of machines for harvesting root crops.

Roots crops are planted in our republic in two seasons, spring and summer. Root crops seeds planted in spring are harvested in the middle of summer, and summer ones are harvested in late October and early November. These two harvesting seasons differ from each other according to soil and climate conditions. This, in turn, complicates the collection of root crops.

In summer, in conditions of low soil moisture, hard cuts appear on the surface of the root-fruit pods. When harvesting root crops, these pieces reduce the level of soil sieving without crushing them in elevators. In the fall, when the soil moisture is higher than the optimum, the soil sticks to the sieves, and as a result, the sieving of the soil in the elevator decreases.

Until now, the vegetable growing sector was not sufficiently provided with technical means, some of the existing machines were outdated, low-quality and late

execution of agrotechnical processes, and required the use of large amounts of manual labor instead.

On a global scale, separate harvesters are being used for each type of tubers. These machines are effective in harvesting roots and fruits with a total cultivated area of more than 35 hectares. However, if we take into account that the average land area for each root crop grower in our country is 5 hectares, root crop machines with the same size produced abroad work at a great loss for the farmer. Because the price of these machines is too expensive for a small farm. Taking into account the above, it is one of the urgent issues to develop a project of a tuber digger with a small size and the ability to harvest several types of tuber [13-15]

3. Results and discussion

Experimental works of the improved universal root-fruit digger, which harvests root crop yield, were conducted at the pilot farm of the Scientific Research Institute, in the farms of Yangiyol district of Tashkent region, Kasbi and Karshi districts of Kashkadarya region. Below are scientific works on the creation of two types of root crop harvester.

Currently, in our Republic, mainly hand-made devices are used for harvesting carrots, which cannot provide the required quality of work. And foreign carrot diggers require a lot of energy and metal consumption. In existing carrot diggers, the sieving process takes place satisfactorily in light and medium soils with normal moisture. In heavy soils, especially in conditions of high or low moisture, sieving devices work inefficiently when harvesting.

To solve the above problems, we proposed a carrot digger equipped with an improved elevator (figure 3).

Plows consist of two main and one intermediate. Transversal pushers (plates) are installed on the elevator wires on the lattice softener fixed to the frame, they are made of metal 3 mm thick and covered with rubber. The guide consists of two parts and is firmly fixed at an angle to the frame. It is made in the form of a grid and covered with rubber.

Figure 3. Construction scheme of the improved carrot digger. 1-digger ploughshares; 2-grid softener; 3rd main elevator; 4-cascade elevator; 5-wheels; 6-guides; 7-slatted couches.

The improved carrot digger above is designed for autumn harvest and is not recommended for summer harvest. Because the soil-climate conditions are hot and dry in our country in the summer season, there is a great possibility of damage to the crop. Improved carrot digger reduces manual labor and increases productivity.

For the summer season, a separate root crop harvester constructive scheme was developed (figure 4). Roots and fruits such as onions, garlic, radishes, beets, turnips, potatoes, carrots can be dug through the universal root crop harvester.

It is recommended to use the root crop harvester for harvesting the crop in the summer season, because the soil-climate conditions in the summer season are hot and dry, which may cause an increase in the level

of damage to the root-fruit when bringing the crop to the surface. One of the reasons for the increased damage is that soil clods are not broken down due to poor irrigation. In the root crop harvester, the crop is less damaged because it is not brought to the surface.

Several types of tubers can be dug through the root crop harvester. In this case, the digging depth can be changed depending on the root crop type due to the change of the part that fastens the wheel support to the main body. Also, the main blade can be set at different angles relative to the horizon. In addition, additional plows can be installed on the main plow depending on the type of root and fruit (figure 5). The disadvantage of the universal tuber digger is the use of manual labor.

Figure 4. Construction scheme of the universal root crop harvester 1-wheels; 2-moving wheel support; 3-wheel support fastening bolt; 4-root crop harvester suspension; 5-column holding the main ploughshare; 6-bolts securing the main plow; 7-main plow; 8-Place for installing additional coulters.

And also taking into account the above and the solution to this problem, we have developed an experimental sample of a potato digger for a walk-behind tractor to carry out agricultural technological processes for growing vegetables and potatoes on small-circuit land and household plots of farm enterprises that most fully meet the agricultural conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

A potato digger is a structure consisting of a body, a conveyor, a knife (ripper), lugs, a wheel axle and conveyor shafts. In front of the case, there is a rack with which the potato digger is attached to walk-behind tractors of various models. On the side walls, there are holes for fastening and adjusting the knife, as well as holes with plain bearings for installing the conveyor

shaft and wheel axle. The wheel axle has holes for positioning and fastening the lugs and a gear wheel for transmitting torque through the gear to the conveyor shaft. On the conveyor shaft, there are sprockets that engage with the conveyor bars, thereby setting it in motion. The optimal tension of the conveyor is achieved with the help of a tensioner and a driven shaft, which is installed in the grooves of the housing [6].

The tasks of the research included the determination of agrotechnical indicators (losses and damage to potato tubers) of the work of a potato digger. In the tests, the qualitative indicators of the potato digger were studied. The figure shows the process of operation of a potato digger (Fig.).

Figure 2. View of the potato digger in the workflow

Characteristics of the test conditions are given in table.1, and the test results were processed and summarized in the table. 3 and 4.

According to the program, the following indicators were determined during the testing process:

- degree of soil separation;
- loss and damage of tubers;
- traction resistance of the potato digger;
- fuel consumption.

The results obtained in the tests are shown in tables 3-4.

The test results show (Table 4) that at the tested speeds, the degree of soil separation in the experimental energy-saving potato digger was 79.8-83.8%. This is ensured by the destruction of soil clods by supporting clod-destroying devices.

4. Conclusion

This study provided a wide range of views which might be helpful for further analyses. This article can be used as a good scientific database for scientists doing scientific research related to root fruits in the field of agriculture. It will be especially useful for young scientists who are just starting to work on this topic. Important information such as which scientists are working in this field in the world, and in which countries this topic is relevant is given.

Based on the conducted scientific research work, we can give the following conclusions:

Taking into account that the average land area for each root crops farmer in Uzbekistan is 5 hectares, large root crops machines produced abroad work at a great loss for farmers. Because the price of these machines is too expensive for a small farm.

Root crops are planted in our republic in two seasons, spring and summer. Root crop seeds planted in spring are harvested in mid-summer, and summer ones are harvested in late October and early November. These two harvesting seasons differ from each other according to soil-climatic conditions. This, in turn, complicates the collection of root crops.

The improved carrot digger is designed for autumn harvesting and is not recommended for summer harvesting. Because the soil-climate conditions are hot and dry in our country in the summer season, there is a great possibility of damage to the crop. Improved carrot digger reduces manual labor and increases productivity.

It is recommended to use the universal root crop harvester for harvesting the crop in the summer season because the hot and dry soil-climate conditions in the summer season can cause an increase in the level of

root crop damage when the crop is brought to the surface. Another reason for increased damage is that soil clods are not crushed due to poor irrigation. In the universal root crop harvester, the crop is less damaged because it is not brought to the surface.

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